

**The Parasite, the Deprived and the Slanderer:
Ideologies and Identity Construction in
Selected 2014 National Conference Discourse in the Nigerian Print Media**

**Olarotimi Daniel Ogungbemi & Oluwadamitan Yewande Okusanya
Department of English, University of Ibadan**

Abstract

The construction of the identity of different people in the different regions of the country can be demonstrated in newspaper texts. This paper examines ideologies and identity construction in the 2014 National Conference discourse in the Nigerian print media. The paper relied on data collected from two national newspapers- The Guardian and The Nation at the National Archives, Ibadan. The data were subjected to critical stylistic analysis. The analysis of the data showed that Nigerians constructed one another from different ideological standpoints that are inimical to unity and oneness of purpose in Nigeria. These ideologies and construction of identity are cleverly presented through critical stylistic tools such as contrasting, presenting opinions, naming and equating, and presenting processes and states in The Nation and The Vanguard newspapers.

Introduction and Review of Relevant Literature

The 2014 National Conference in Nigeria was an answer to the insistent calls by social and human rights advocates, ethnic groups, religious bodies, and opposition parties for a sovereign national conference to address national questions bordering on marginalisation, structural violence and political reforms. Achieving a united and stable political system is a serious challenge to the Nigerian state (Ajayi, 2006). Marginalisation, unequal distribution of resources and power, and official injustice are recurrent issues in Nigeria, a country divided multi-ethnically and multi-culturally.

National conference is an official gathering of interest groups, including sub nationalities and sectional representations in a polity. Ajayi (2006) opines that a national conference can be gingered by the imperatives of engineering a new constitution or as a way of forging common solutions to perceived national problems, particularly in divided societies such as Nigeria, where ethnic and other sectional cleavages have become constraints to the emergence of a sense of nationalism and national integration. More often than not, a national conference has the power to take any decisions on the issues before it and sets its own agenda. When this happens, the government has little or no power on the conference because the delegates of such conference are, in most cases, nominated by the

diverse interest groups of the civil society. These interest groups could include representatives of ethnic groups, political parties and associations, labour, students, farmers, women and religious groups, and even that of government. In Nigeria, studies on national conference discourse are relatively few. Utim (2005) cited in Ogoma (2014) is a study on Nigerian federalism, national reform conference and conflict resolution: a diatribe on the missing links and Nwaoga et al. (2014) is a study on ethno-religious pluralism and the challenge of national unity in Nigeria. Existing studies on national conferences in Nigeria have largely been non-linguistic as the above shows. Therefore, this study becomes necessary as it examines the underlying ideologies and the linguistic construction of the identity of some of the actors and participants of the 2014 national conference discourse in two Nigerian newspapers, *The Nation* and *The Guardian*. This study opines that the construction of the identity of different people in the different regions of the country, which is ideological, can be demonstrated linguistically in newspaper texts. The aim of this study is to elicit these hidden ideologies and to show what linguistic features are used in the texts of newspaper articles on the 2014 national conference to trigger these ideologies. In section 2 below, we present our theoretical perspectives; in section 3, we examine the methods and analytical framework for the study. In section 4, we explore the underlying ideologies and the linguistic construction of the identity of some of the actors and participants of the 2014 national conference discourse in *The Nation* and *The Guardian* newspapers, and in section 5, we conclude the paper.

Theoretical Perspectives

This work is anchored on Jeffries' (2010) Critical Stylistic model. The theory 'Critical Stylistics' was coined by Jeffries (2007) when she explored (i) the hegemonic discourses on the female body in society and (ii) whether feminist ideologies have successfully been incorporated into these hegemonic discourses. Critical Stylistics aims at assembling how a text represents reality. This is based on the fact that 'there is a level at which texts organize the world we experience and that this is demonstrable in the words and structures of the texts themselves' (Jeffries, 2010a). Jeffries (2010a) opines that 'language is essentially a finely balanced combination of rules and broken rules, where the fact that there is no one-to-one form-function relationship is the key to many of the most useful and life-enhancing aspects of language, such as the writing of poetry and the use of metaphor in daily life, as well as of the more negative aspects, such as lying and manipulation' (2010a: 44).

Further, Critical Stylistics acts as a bridge between CDA and Stylistics by seizing and further developing the Critical Linguistics approach to text analysis.

Therefore, it can be regarded as another approach to CDA, and can be grouped under Critical Language Studies, because both CDA and Critical Stylistics aim at revealing ideologies and power relations in discourse. In addition, Critical Stylistics can be regarded not merely as an approach to CDA but also a further development of CDA. While CDA has a politically motivated view of power relations and focuses on the question of who has the power to determine hegemonic discourses by having access to knowledge and the media (as a means of text production), Critical Stylistics is based on text analysis aiming at revealing power relations by working on the textual level.

Critical Stylistics provides a set of analytical tools which, when followed along, will reveal the ideologies hidden in the text without the need for subjectively looking for them in order to verify preconceived assumptions. These analytical tools include: Naming and Describing, Representing Actions/Events/States, Equating and Contrasting, Exemplifying and Enumerating, Prioritising, Implying and Assuming, Negating, Hypothesising, Presenting other's speech and thoughts, Representing time, space and society.

Methods and Analytical Framework

Nigerian newspaper reports constituted our main source of data. Data were gathered from March 2014 to May 2014. The data comprised of news reports, and opinion columns on the 2014 National Conference. One hundred and twenty articles and reports on some of the issues at stake on the national conference were gathered and read. The newspapers were drawn from the newspaper archives of the NISER's Library in Ibadan. Out of these, only 30 articles were purposively selected for analysis. Specifically, *The Nation* and *The Guardian* newspapers were selected for the study because they dedicated regular columns to the National Conference news and reports and they enjoy a measure of prestige among a cross section of Nigerian readership.

The Critical Stylistic framework in this study is capable of facilitating a systematic and detailed linguistic analysis on the 2014 National Conference, because of its focus on the hidden ideological orientations in the discourse. We shall, at this juncture, illustrate the steps that are needed to realise the purpose of this study through the Critical Stylistic framework. Four Critical Stylistic tools through which identity construction and the underlying ideologies in the 2014 National Conference are revealed are: contrasting, presenting opinions, naming and equating, and presenting processes and states.

Analysis and Findings

Contrasting

Identity can be constructed through the employment of contrasts, either by creating opposition or by negation. Jeffries, (2010a) claims that negation is a sub-category of opposition beside other sub-categories of opposition as antonymous sense relation, syntactic trigger, etc. Opposition puts two events, states or existences into contrast to each other, negation opposes non-events against events, non-states against states or nonexistence against existence and thereby constructs 'unrealized worlds' (Nahajec, 2009: 109). One of the most important of the linguistic-cognitive structures by which we characterize and organize our world, and thus also our world-view'are opposites (Jeffries, 2010b: 26). Examples in our data are shown below.

Text 1

He alleged that Nwabueze's comments were geared towards supporting the Yoruba agenda, while undermining the progress of his kinsmen who are the endangered species and dregs of Nigerian society.

(The Guardian, 18. 02. 14. Pp. 4)

Text 2

Insiders said that Northern delegates insisted on reduction in derivation principle while their Southern counterparts, especially those from the Southsouth wanted increment.

(The Nation, 13.05.2014)

Text 3

The present system is not profitable because Oyo gets a federal allocation of N4 billion monthly for over eight million people while

Bayelsa gets N22 billion for just 700, 000 people. This is something we should address critically at the conference.

(The Guardian, 18.02.2014. pp 4)

Text 4

The Co- Chairmen said the South-East zone deserves to have six states like other zones that have six or seven states each.

(The Nation, 27.04.2014)

In Text 1, two major tribes in the country are represented, the Yoruba and the Igbo. Nwabueze, a renowned constitutional lawyer, who is Igbo, is accused of lending his support to a direct rival the Yoruba at the expense of the progress of his own people. The sentence contrasts Nwabueze's support for a direct rival and opposition against the progress of his own people who politically have not benefitted as the said rival. The syntactic trigger for opposition in this sentence is the conjunction *while*. The choice of verb tense (past tense in the first clause (*were geared*) and present auxiliary in the second (*are*)) underlines the oppositional meaning: Nwabueze's support for a rival against his own very people. Out of the context in the article it becomes clear that tension exists between the Igbo and the Yoruba politically. This implicates that an Igbo son or daughter should not be seen as lending his support for the Yoruba or other ethnic groups whose interest does not align with theirs. This constructs Nwabueze as a betrayer of his people to another group in the country, the Yoruba.

Text 2 involves delegates from the northern part of the country and delegates from the southsouth geo-political zone. That the Northern delegates are seen as one united front as opposed to delegates from the three geo-political zones in the north is significant. The Northern delegate's demand contrasts the demand and stand of the delegates from the southsouth geo-political zones. Again as in Text 1, the syntactic trigger for opposition is still the conjunction *while*. The choice of the verb tense in the two clauses – *insisted* and *wanted* both in the past tense help to construct the oppositional meaning. To insist conveys persistence and to want conveys desire. This shows that issues concerning the derivation principle must have been on for some time. From the oppositional meaning created by the two verbs in the clauses, it appears the southsouth geo-political zone benefits more from the derivation principle than the geo-political zones in the north. The north, although

consists of different geo-political zones, is constructed as one big united zone in the country which could speak with one voice; by associating the north with the use of the verb- *insisted*, the zone is also constructed as a powerful zone.

In Text 3, the attention is on two states in Nigeria which are significant to the country, Nigeria. The two states are Oyo in the south west geo-political zone and Bayelsa in the south south geo-political zone. Oyo is seen as the political headquarters of the Yoruba while Bayelsa is one of the states where large quantity of crude oil is found in Nigeria. The conjunction *while* is also deployed as the syntactic trigger of opposition in the complex sentence. The revenue allocation system favours Bayelsa State more than Oyo State. The choice of the verb tense in both subordinate clauses in the sentence (gets) underlines the oppositional meaning: Oyo State with over 8 million people receives less than Bayelsa State with less than 2 million people. On the one hand, Oyo State is constructed as a state that is deprived and cheated by the Federal government. On the other, Bayelsa State is constructed as benefiting unduly from the Federal government.

Text 4 shows an opposition at the intra-clause level in comparison to the examples in Texts 1-3 where the opposition is to be found at the inter-clause level. In Text 4 above, the south east geo-political zone is constructed in opposition to other geo-political zones in the country. The south east geo-political zone is constructed through a main clause while the other zones are constructed in the subordinate clause. The naming choice for the concerned region (south east zone) provides a contrast to the other zones which are not named at all. These naming choices/ styles construct the south east zone which is the affected zone as more important but a neglected region whereas the other zones which have more states in them are constructed as not as important as the south east zone.

Presenting opinions

One way to present opinions is to quote other people's utterances. There are different ways to present their verbiage according to the model introduced by Leech and Short (1981) and further developed by Semino and Short (2004). The two

most frequently used options are Direct Speech (DS) and Indirect Speech (IS) which contains the verbiage 'as a version of the supposed verbatim speech' (Jeffries, 2010a: 134). Examples of DS can be found in the following statements. Text 5 is uttered by the president of Committee 21, an Igbo socio-political group Senator Annie Okonkwo:

Text 5

“Any opportunity for a national jaw-jaw of this dimension is better than war-war. The potency to correct structural and social injustices is best served through dialogue than the violence of warfare. People must appreciate that it is better late than never.”

(The Nation, 11.03.2014. pp 5)

Text 6

Secretary of the Igbo Leaders of Thought, Prof. Elochukwu Amucheazi said of Nwabueze:

“He is simply playing the music of the Yoruba people. There is no case in court concerning Ohanaeze. We are not divided. Chief Garry Igariwey remains our president-General. Nwabueze is a good constitutional lawyer, he has grown and does not want anyone else to grow, but he should know that Igboland has good lawyers today.”

(The Guardian, 18.02.2014. pp 4)

Text 7

The General Overseer of Vineyard Christian Ministries, Archbishop John Osa-Oni calling on the Muslims to reconsider their utterances said:

“The National Conference is not about any religion but about Nigeria. And in Nigeria, there are Christians and other sects. You can’t be putting pressure on the President because this country is neither about Christians nor about any other religion. This country is not for Muslims and it is not for Christians. It is for everybody.”(The Guardian, 29.03.2014. pp 6)

Text 8

The Lamido of Adamawa, Dr MuhammaduBarkindo Mustapha continued:

“If something happens and the country disintegrates-God forbid – many of those who are shouting their heads off will have nowhere to go. I and the people of Adamawa- and many others- have somewhere to go. I am the Lamido of Adamawa and my kingdom transcends Nigeria and Cameroon. A large part of my kingdom is in the republic of Cameroun, apart from my kingdom in Adamawa.

Statements in Text 5, credited to the president of Committee 21, an Igbo socio-political group, Senator Annie Okonkwo construct some groups in the country as more powerful than the others. Words such as *structural* and *social injustices*, give credence to the fact some regions or groups in the country are more favoured than others. The statements are given weight by being officially uttered by the president of an Igbo socio-political group who has a vested interest in creating such a construction because the Igbo believe they have been marginalized since the end of the Civil War in the country. His statements also construct the country as a tension soaked one.

Text 6 constructs the Yoruba as slanderers. They talk ill of the Igbo; slandering them. This submission is given weight by being officially uttered by the secretary of the Igbo Leaders of Thought, an authoritative person who has a vested interest in creating such a construction. This could be a very manipulative way of implanting other people’s views upon the reader because in this context the reader assumes that

the secretary is likely to have insight and know all the facts about the Igbo organisation, and his statement is therefore not to be questioned. Nwabueze is also constructed as a selfish and inconsistent Igbo who allows himself to be manipulated by the Yoruba.

In Text 7, the Muslims are constructed as troublesome and always believing they own the country. The use of Direct Speech in contrast to other options (for example Indirect Speech), constructs the notion that this utterance is faithful to the original utterance which, of course, is unlikely to be checked by most readers. If you are a Christian, it would take some effort to disagree with the General Overseer of Vineyard Christian Ministries, Archbishop John Osa-Oni who said those words. Not only the illocutionary force behind the utterance but also the locution is presented and this creates the illusion of faithfulness. Direct Speech in combination with quoting an official person constructs this utterance as a given fact rather than an opinion which can be contested.

Text 8 constructs the most of the people in Nigeria as vagabond. The Lamido of Adamawa believes that he and other countless people in the north have places to fall back on should Nigeria disintegrate. The statements credited to the Lamido is given weight by being officially uttered by a traditional leader in the north, an authoritative person who has a vested interest in creating such a construction.

The following example shows the combined use of DS and IS which is even more manipulative because it blends verbatim quotations with a reworded version of the original verbiage:

Text 9

The South West Chairman of the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN), Archbishop Magnus Atilade, believes most of the delegates are recycled elements that brought the nation down to her knees in the first place. “If you carefully look through the list, you will see that most of these people have been there. They brought us to where we are now. I don’t see how they can fix this nation or propose radical changes that we need,” he stated.

(The Nation, 16.03.2014. pp 11)

Text 10

But the Lamido of Adamawa, Dr Muhammadu Barkindo Mustapha, reportedly side-tracked the issues and delivered a speech which other delegates saw as a well rehearsed speech to frighten the South. He was reported to have warned that the North should not be pushed to the wall and that if they were, they would simply walk out of the conference. To underscore his seriousness, Dr. Mustapha was quoted to have said: “When the North walks out of the conference, there would be great consequences for the country.”

In Text 9 DS, marked by inverted commas and embedded in the IS, both present the South West Chairman of the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN), Archbishop Magnus Atilade’s opinion of the delegates for the national conference. Here again an authoritative person, a religious leader, is quoted which assigns the judgement a high value. The reader is unable to assess if this blend of the chairman’s words and their reformulation still contain the original illocutionary force, which is the underlying intention of the speaker. At the same time, it allows the writer to merge those parts of the locution which serve the intended construction of the delegates and leave others out. Thereby the writer is able to hide his own opinion by purporting to quote other people. The delegates are constructed as possessing certain negative character features. Their being negative leading figures is underpinned by the final statements *They brought us to where we are now. I don't see how they can fix this nation or propose radical changes that we need.*

In Text 10 also, DS, marked by inverted commas and embedded in the IS, is used to represent the opinion of the Lamido of Adamawa, Dr Muhammadu Barkindo Mustapha in particular and that of the North in general. The opinion is assigned a high value because it is attributed to a traditional leader in the North. In the process, the journalist is able to hide his/her own opinion by purporting to quote others. The North is constructed as very powerful. Walking out of the conference would have consequences on the country.

Naming and Equating

This conceptual category (Jeffries, 2010a: 17ff) deals with the construction of noun phrases which consist of a head noun, sometimes accompanied by pre- or postmodifiers, which construct the referent.

Text 11

And in any case when did the south ever agree to assume the role of a wealthy yet submissive and timid wife that has been systematically and consistently cheated, raped and sodomised by a parasitic, domineering and arrogant northern husband?

(The Guardian, 02.02.2014, pp 33)

Text 12

And what makes matter worse is that this is a habitually lazy husband who is not only poverty-stricken but also barely educated and ill-prepared for the 21st century.

(The Guardian, 02.02.2014, pp 33)

Text 11 contains some target words, *parasitic*, *domineering* and *arrogant*. The extended noun phrase *a parasitic, domineering and arrogant northern husband* makes it possible to 'package up' (Jeffries, 2010a: 19) the information that the northern part of the country is lordly and lording it over the southern region even though the former is constructed as a moocher. The reader is unlikely to question the information but rather takes this information about the North for granted. The four premodifiers are adjectives. The adjective is 'the most typical vehicle for characterizing in English' (Jeffries, 2007: 64). The adjective *parasitic*, *domineering* and *arrogant* convey a negative construction of the northerners. These kinds of adjectives are purely descriptive.

Text 12 is also a construction of the North, who is said to be the husband of the South. The wife (south) must have gone through a lot in the hands of the husband. The writer through the noun phrase *a habitually lazy husband* constructs the north as

always feeding off the South (wife). The North is accused of relying on the resources and wealth in the South. This is achieved through the use of different linguistic devices. In the beginning, the employment of the indefinite article (*a*) and the use of an adjectival phrase (*habitually lazy*) which serves together with the article as modifiers for the headword *husband* construct an irresponsible husband.

Presenting processes and states

The model of transitivity used here is derived from Simpson (1993; 2004), as his explication is accessible, and is informed by a symbiosis of stylistic and CDA approaches to text analysis. According to Simpson, transitivity “shows how speakers encode in language their mental picture of reality and how they account for their experience of the world around them.” (Simpson, 1993: 88). Simpson (1993) groups processes into different categories ‘according to whether they represent actions, speech, states of mind or simply states of being’ (1993: 88). In our data, there are instances of relational processes and Material Action Intention as a material process. Relational processes refer to processes of *being*’ (Simpson, 1993: 91), and include a carrier and an attribute. The following example illustrates this:

Text 13

“I believe Nigeria’s unity is negotiable. Our unity today is that of cat and mouse,” he stressed.

(The Guardian, 02.01. 2014. Pp 3)

Text 14

The very basis of our being together from the beginning in 1914 is faulty.

(The Guardian, 04.02.2014. pp 2)

The two texts (13 and 14) refer to the unity of Nigeria. In Text 13, the unity is said to be negotiable. Thereby *Nigeria’s unity* is the carrier and *negotiable* is the attribute. Further, *our unity today* is the carrier while that of cat and mouse is the *attribute*. This transitivity category is used to describe conditions the country is in to illustrate the level of disunity in the country. The cat and mouse relationship that exists among the different tribes in the country constructs a country that is greatly disunited. Text 14 too conveys the same idea. It traces the history of the problems in the country. *The*

very basis of our being together from the beginning in 1914 is the carrier while *faulty* is the attribute. In Text 14, the problem of the country is traced to the marriage of different peoples whose cultures and ways are totally different from one another by the colonial power.

An example of Material Action Intention can be found in the following examples:

Text 15

The north threatened to walk out of the on-going national conference.

(The Nation, 27.03.2014. pp 2)

The clause of Text 15 (The north threatened to walk out of the on-going national conference) is an example of Material Action Intention with *north* being the actor, *threatened to walk out* the process and *the on-going national conference* the goal (Simpson, 1993: 89). This constructs the North as a very important national and political player that is vital to the success of the national conference.

Text 16

National conference splits Igbo elite (headline)

(The Guardian, 18.02.2014. pp 5)

This headline is rendered in the active voice. The subject *national conference* is the actor of a process (*splits*) and the goal of the action *Igbo elite*. The division among the Igbo elite is foregrounded through the active voice to construct the national conference as very important and the Igbo elite as not united.

Text 17

CAN accuses Kutigi of pursuing Islamic agenda

(The Guardian, 23.4.2014. pp 2)

Here the target word *Kutigi* is the goal acted upon by CAN who is the actor in this sentence which constructs Kutigi, a Muslim and the chairman of the National Conference of being biased and favouring fellow Muslims at the expense of the

Christians. This sentence illustrates the use of the active voice and Material Action Intention.

Conclusion

This study has shown how the participants of the 2014 National Conference discourse are constructed linguistically in *The Nation* and *The Guardian* newspapers in Nigeria. The overall research question, namely, how do the participants in the 2014 national conference discourse use language to construct one another in the Nigerian print media was answered via the application of critical stylistic approach to the data. Jeffries' Critical Stylistics on which the study is anchored has been justified in this study. Critical Stylistic tools such as contrasting, presenting opinions, naming and equating, and presenting processes and states account for the underlying ideologies and the linguistic construction of identity.

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